

Synthesis of Some New 2,4,6-Triaryl Substituted Pyridines via Pyridinium Ylides

R. S. TEWARI* and N. K. MISRA

Department of Chemistry, H. B. Technological Institute, Kanpur-208 002

Manuscript received 13 April 1979, revised 14 March 1980, accepted 28 January 1981

Reactions of 4-methoxy phenacyl pyridinium ylide and 4-chlorophenacyl pyridinium ylide with different substituted α - β unsaturated ketones gave a wide variety of 2,4,6-triaryl substituted pyridines which are expected to possess marked biological activities. The reaction presumably proceeds via formation of 1,5-dionyl pyridinium intermediate (4a-n). Ammonium acetate in acetic acid was used as cyclization agent. The structures of the products were confirmed either by nmr or by ir spectrum analysis.

TSCHITSCHIBABIN¹ was first to introduce the synthesis of substituted pyridines but because of undesirable side reactions Kröhnke *et al*^{2,3} has given an improved method for such cyclizations.

Continuing our studies on ylides^{4,5} in the present communication, we wish to report the synthesis of some new 2,4,6-triaryl substituted pyridines using Kröhnke's method.

Experimental

Melting points were measured on a Gallen Kamp apparatus and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer in potassium bromide. The nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were run using a Varian A-60 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Analytical samples were purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina. Purity was checked by thin layer chromatography (tlc).

Pyridinium salts were prepared by treatment of α -bromoketones and pyridine in benzene at reflux temperature.

Preparation of 2,4,6-triaryl substituted pyridines :

A general procedure was used in all the reactions. To a stirred solution of 3 mmol of pyridinium salts (1a-b) in 10 ml of glacial acetic acid in presence of ammonium acetate was added gradually a solution of α - β unsaturated ketone (3a-n; 3 mmol.) in 50 ml of glacial acetic acid under an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The reaction mixture was stirred at reflux temperature for six hours and was kept at room temperature overnight. It was then washed with ice cold water (30 ml), the precipitated product so obtained was washed twice with methanol and was recrystallized by appropriate solvent mentioned in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

p-Methoxy phenacyl pyridinium ylide (2a) and *p*-chloro phenacyl pyridinium ylide (2b) were generated *in situ* by dehydrohalogenation of their precursors, *p*-methoxy phenacyl pyridinium bromide (1a) and *p*-chloro phenacyl pyridinium bromide (1b). The reaction of 2a-b with various substituted α - β unsaturated ketones in acetic acid using ammonium acetate as cyclization agent yielded some new 2,4,6-triaryl substituted pyridines (5a-n) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The ylide carbanion undergoes Michael type of addition on α - β unsaturated carbonyl systems to yield 1,5-dionyl pyridinium derivative (4a-n) which on further reaction with ammonium acetate gave various 2,4,6-triaryl substituted pyridines.

All the pyridines are listed in Table 1. The structures of the resulting pyridines are supported either by ir or by nmr data given in Table 2.

* To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF 2,4,6-TRIARYL SUBSTITUTED PYRIDINES(5a-n)

Compound	Molecular Formula	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Yield %	m.p. °C	Recrystn. Solvent	Analysis : Found (Calcd)%		
								C	H	N
5a	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₂	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	60	104-5	Py/MeOH	81.92 (81.88)	6.05 (6.03)	3.69 (3.52)
b	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₂	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	55	129-30	"	78.54 (78.58)	5.81 (5.79)	3.54 (3.52)
c	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ NO ₂ Cl	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	65	144-5	"	74.76 (74.71)	4.96 (4.98)	3.46 (3.48)
d	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ NO ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	3,4-(MeO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	50	80-2	"	79.28 (79.21)	6.13 (6.11)	3.44 (3.42)
e	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ NOCl ₂	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	73	195	"	71.14 (71.11)	4.22 (4.19)	3.43 (3.45)
f	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₂ Cl	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	3,4-(MeO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	58	118-20	"	72.32 (72.30)	5.11 (5.09)	3.26 (3.24)
g	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ NO ₂ S	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	3,4-(MeO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	2-C ₄ H ₉ S	52	97-8	Py/MeOH/H ₂ O	71.49 (71.46)	5.20 (5.21)	3.49 (3.47)
h	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ NOCl ₂	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	75	176-8	Py	71.14 (71.11)	4.17 (4.19)	3.46 (3.45)
i	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ NOCl	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	60	168-70	Py/MeOH	77.86 (77.82)	5.20 (5.18)	3.65 (3.63)
j	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₂ Cl	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	3,4-(MeO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	50	128-30	"	72.32 (72.30)	5.11 (5.08)	3.22 (3.24)
k	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₂ Cl	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	3,4-(MeO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	45	134	"	75.12 (75.09)	5.32 (5.29)	3.34 (3.36)
l	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ NO ₂ Cl ₂	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	3,4-OH ₂ O ₂ C ₆ H ₃	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	48	160-1	"	68.60 (68.57)	3.58 (3.57)	3.31 (3.33)
m	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ NCl ₂	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	-C ₆ H ₅	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	52	126	"	73.42 (73.40)	3.96 (3.98)	3.74 (3.73)
n	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ NCIS	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	-C ₆ H ₅	2-C ₄ H ₉ S	45	95	"	68.59 (68.57)	4.04 (4.03)	4.71 (4.70)

Py = C₅H₅N

TABLE 2—NMR AND IR DATA OF 2,4,6-TRIARYL SUBSTITUTED PYRIDINES (5a-n)

Compound	NMR data (CDCl ₃)		IR data (KBr), cm ⁻¹		
	aliphatic H	aromatic H	OH Stretching Vibrations	C=O Vibrations	O=N Vibrations
4a	2.33 _s CH ₃ 3.64 _s 3.73 _s OCH ₃	6.60-8.08 _m			
4b	3.88 _s OCH ₃	6.96-8.21 _m			
4c	3.64-3.82 _d OCH ₃	6.63-8.02 _m			
4d	3.82-4.06 _m OCH ₃	6.88-8.19 _m			
4e	3.74 _s OCH ₃	6.65-8.03 _m			
4f	—	—	2948	1598	1520
4g	3.84-4.06 _m OCH ₃	6.90-8.34 _m			
4h	3.77 _s OCH ₃	6.76-8.10 _m			
4i	2.42 _s CH ₃ 3.82 _s OCH ₃	6.98-8.24 _m			
4j	3.72-3.88 _m OCH ₃	6.56-8.15 _m			
4k	2.33 _s CH ₃ 3.76-3.86 _m OCH ₃	6.64-8.11 _m			
4l	6.00 _s OCH ₃ O	6.96-8.10 _m			
4m	—	—	3020	1600	1525
4n	—	—	3050	1595	1540

s=singlet, d=doublet, m=multiplet.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank the Director, H.B. Technological Institute, Kanpur for providing necessary facilities. One of the authors (N.K.M) is thankful to U. G. C., New Delhi for financial assistance and also to Principal, D. B. S. College, Kanpur for providing facilities for research.

References

1. A. E. TSCHITSCHIBABIN, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1937, 4, 1826; *J. Russ. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 37, 1229; *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1924, 107, 122.
2. F. KRÖHNKE and W. ZECHNY, *Angew Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1962, 1, 626.
3. F. KRÖHNKE, *Synthesis*, 1976, 1.
4. P. S. KENDURKAR and R. S. TEWARI, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1973, 29b, 552; *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 1974, 19, 184.
5. R. S. TEWARI and K. O. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 829.